

Numerical Simulation of a Moving-Bed Reactor Using Strontium Chloride Hydrates for Heat Storage Applications

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Abstract

A comprehensive numerical analysis of a moving-bed thermochemical reactor using $\text{SrCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{SrCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ for low-temperature heat storage applications is presented. The reactor operates in open mode, in which humid air flows through a downward-moving salt bed. Fluid flow, reaction kinetics, and coupled heat and mass transfer are modeled in COMSOL Multiphysics under different boundary conditions.

The effects of inlet air humidity, solid velocity, and airflow rate on the reactor's thermal performance were investigated. The bed temperature and heat output increase from 33 °C to 44 °C and from 0.2 kW/m³ to 3 kW/m³, respectively, as the humidity rises from 6 g/kg to 12 g/kg. The reactor achieves its best performance at an airflow rate of 110 m³/h.

The model successfully predicts experimental outcomes, thereby enhancing reactor design. In addition, it provides valuable insights into improving thermochemical energy storage systems for building heating applications.

Keywords

Moving Bed Reactor, Salt Hydrate, Solid-Gas Reaction, Thermochemical Energy Storage, Strontium Chloride, Humid air

1 Introduction

Cities consume between 60% and 80% of total energy, with buildings accounting for 36% of that consumption, and are responsible for a large share of CO₂ emissions [1]. Solar energy provides one of the most effective pathways to reduce fossil-fuel consumption in buildings [2]. The primary limitations of solar energy include intermittency (no power at night or on cloudy days) and the high cost of battery storage systems [3], which has led to significant research into energy storage technologies [4]. Among these, thermochemical energy storage systems (TCES) utilize chemical reactions in three stages: endothermic dissociation, storage of the reaction products, and exothermic recombination of the dissociated products [5].

Thermochemical reactors can operate in both closed and open modes. In closed mode, salt and water vapor react under vacuum conditions. In open mode, moist air flows through the reactive solid bed at atmospheric pressure. Operating under vacuum introduces significant design challenges, whereas open-mode operation eliminates the need for components such as evaporators, condensers, and water storage reservoirs [6]. Moreover, in open TCES systems, it is essential to control air humidity and temperature to prevent salt agglomeration and deliquescence.

Farcot et al. [7] performed a 2D analysis in COMSOL Multiphysics on a moving-bed reactor in which SrCl_2 solid particles move along the reactor height while air flows across the cross-section. A sharp reaction front is formed, which is highly sensitive to humidity, inlet air pressure, and solid flow rate. Their results show that the continuous operation of the moving-bed reactor enables regulation of the thermal output, making it suitable for large-scale applications such as district heating. Wen et al. [8] analyzed a moving-bed reactor using silica gel under three-phase flow (air, water, and solid). The moving-bed design provides steady and homogeneous heat release by mitigating reverse heat transfer and maintaining a consistent high-temperature region. An increase in inlet temperature from 23 °C to 38 °C resulted in a 40.03% improvement in conversion efficiency.

Farcot et al. [9] conducted experiments on a moving-bed reactor using the $\text{SrBr}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{SrBr}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ system for building-scale solar heat storage. Reactor temperatures reached a maximum of 41 °C, while the specific heating power ranged between 1.7 and 4.6 kW/m³. The output power in the moving-bed configuration increased by 55% compared to a packed-bed reactor. Although previous experimental studies have demonstrated the feasibility of moving-bed reactors using salt hydrates, they are limited by short test durations, operational challenges, and inhomogeneous solid flow. Furthermore, the complex coupling between operating parameters and reactor performance is difficult to fully capture experimentally.

In this context, the present study develops a numerical model of a moving-bed reactor using COMSOL Multiphysics to simulate coupled heat and mass transfer under realistic operating conditions. Key parameters, including air humidity, airflow rate, and solid velocity, are analyzed in terms of useful heat delivered to the air, bed temperature, and outlet air temperature. To ensure comparability with experimental data, simulations are conducted over an 8-hour period. This approach provides valuable insights for improving the design and scalability of thermochemical energy storage systems for building heating applications.

2 System Overview

A 3D numerical analysis has been performed on a moving-bed reactor. A solid ($\text{SrCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ salt hydrate) flows from the top to the bottom of the reactor, while moist air flows from the left side to the right side of the reactor (see Fig. 1). Thermal energy is then transferred to the district heating system via a heat exchanger.

Cold, humid air enters the bed and interacts with the solid material. Heat is released during the hydration reaction and is carried by the air, which transfers this thermal energy to the district heating system.

3 Simulations

The incoming humid air is at 30 °C, with relative humidities (RH) of 0.4, 0.6, and 0.8, corresponding to humidity levels of 6, 9, and 12 g/kg, respectively. The airflow rates range from 80 to 140 m³/h.

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Figure 1: Schematic diagram of the moving bed reactor.

The solid salt moves downward at a velocity of 0.5 cm/h, which is considered the optimal value to achieve full hydration in the reactor, based on comparisons with a higher velocity of 1.5 cm/h.

The solid–gas reaction between $\text{SrCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and water vapor to form $\text{SrCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is considered:

Table 1 shows the size of the moving-bed reactor.

Table 1: The moving bed reactor's size.

Parameter	Value	Dimension
H1	3100	mm
H2	675	mm
H3	1600	mm
H4	120	mm
H5	100	mm
H6	950	mm
H7	597	mm
L1	950	mm
W1	650	mm
D	160	mm
θ	70	°

3.1 Governing equations

Molar balance equations of the conversion of water vapor in the porous medium can be obtained from:

$$\varepsilon n_h \frac{\partial y_h}{\partial t} = \phi_v (1 - y_v) - n_h u_h \nabla y_v \quad (2)$$

Salt conversion balance equation describes the evolution of the salt's hydration state:

$$(1 - \varepsilon) \frac{\partial X}{\partial t} = -\frac{\phi_v}{v} - u_s \nabla X \quad (3)$$

$$\phi_v = -v(1 - \varepsilon) n_s \dot{X}_a \quad (4)$$

In this study, the Brinkman equations, a non-Darcian formulation that extends Darcy's law to account for shear effects, are applied to model fluid flow through the porous thermochemical reactor.

This approach is suitable for porous media with moderate permeability and enables the capture of velocity gradients within the reactor domain [10].

$$\rho(\mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla)\mathbf{u} = \nabla \cdot (-p\mathbf{I} + \mu(\nabla\mathbf{u} + (\nabla\mathbf{u})^T)) - \mu\alpha\mathbf{u} + \rho\mathbf{F} \quad (5)$$

To model thermal energy exchange in the moving-bed reactor, heat transfer at the fluid–solid interfaces is considered. In the fluid domain, heat transfer is governed by the energy conservation equation [11]:

$$\rho C_p \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla T + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{q} = Q + Q_p + Q_{vd} \quad (6)$$

where $\mathbf{q} = -k\nabla T$ is the conductive heat flux, and Q , Q_p , and Q_{vd} represent volumetric heat sources due to chemical reactions, pressure work, and viscous dissipation, respectively. In the solid domain, the governing equation simplifies to [11]:

$$\rho C_p \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{q} = Q + Q_{ted} \quad (7)$$

where Q_{ted} represents the effects of thermal expansion, which are neglected in the present study. The heat source term Q corresponds to the exothermic hydration reaction of SrBr_2 and is implemented as:

$$Q = R_{\text{reac}} \Delta H_{\text{hydration}} \quad (8)$$

The reaction rate, \dot{X}_a , is given by [9, 12]:

$$\dot{X}_a = A_r \exp\left(-\frac{E_a}{RT}\right) (1 - X) \left(1 - \frac{p_v}{p_{eq}}\right) \quad (9)$$

where A_r is the pre-exponential factor, equal to 1.63×10^4 [13], E_a is the activation energy, equal to 56.6 kJ/mol [13], and R refers to the universal gas constant. c_{in} denotes the inlet water vapor concentration, p_{eq} is the equilibrium vapor pressure (calculated using the Clausius–Clapeyron equation), and F_b is the bypass factor accounting for unreacted airflow.

This formulation ensures that the heat source is active only in regions where the vapor pressure exceeds the equilibrium threshold and where effective contact between air and salt occurs [14].

$$p_{eq} = p_{\text{ref}} \exp\left(-\frac{\Delta H_0}{RT} + \frac{\Delta S_0}{R}\right) \quad (10)$$

Energy conversion equation in the central zone of the moving bed reactor as a porous medium is given by:

$$(\rho C_p)_{\text{eff}} \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (-k_{\text{eff}} \nabla T) + \nabla \cdot (\rho C_p \mathbf{u} T) = Q \quad (11)$$

$$(\rho C_p)_{\text{eff}} = (1 - \varepsilon)(\rho C_p)_s + \varepsilon(\rho C_p)_v \quad (12)$$

$$k_{\text{eff}} = (1 - \varepsilon)k_s + \varepsilon k_v \quad (13)$$

For solid reactive salt:

$$(\rho C_p)_s = (1 - X)(\rho C_p)_{s1} + X(\rho C_p)_{s0} \quad (14)$$

$$k_s = (1 - X)k_{s1} + Xk_{s0} \quad (15)$$

where subscripts s1 and s0 denote the hexahydrate and monohydrate states, respectively. The useful heat delivered to the air, \dot{q}_{heat} , can be given by [9]:

$$\dot{q}_{\text{heat}} = \dot{m}_{a,\text{in}} [(C_{p,a} + w_{\text{out}} C_{p,v}) T_{\text{out}} - (C_{p,a} + w_{\text{in}} C_{p,v}) T_{\text{in}}] \quad (16)$$

3.2 Validation

In COMSOL, the physics-controlled mesh approach automatically generates a mesh and provides adaptive refinement based on the model's physics. In regions with higher resolution that require the inclusion of corners or areas with high gradients in temperature, pressure, or velocity, the mesh is refined. Mesh independence was achieved at 644,783 elements (See Table 2).

Table 2: Grid independence study

Grid type	Number of grids	T_{bed} (°C)	T_{out} (°C)	Heat (kW/m ³)	w_{out} (g/kg)
Coarse grid	302,554	—	—	—	—
Medium grid	644,783	1.84%	1.17%	0.93%	1.45%
Finer grid	2,962,982	0.68%	0.23%	0.016%	0.47%

To assess the validity and accuracy of the results, they were compared with the experimental data presented by Farcot et al. [7]. The comparison confirms that the model is suitable for analyzing thermochemical energy storage (TCES) systems based on hydrated salts. The setup parameters used in the model are summarized in Tables 3 and 4.

Table 3: Setup parameters used in numerical simulation

Parameter	Value
$T_{in,air}$	22 °C
$Q_{in,air}$	93 m ³ /h
u_s	0.5 cm/h
ρ_{salt}	3500 kg/m ³
k_{salt}	0.5 W/(m · K)
$C_{p,salt}$	970 J/(g · K)
Porosity	0.317
Permeability (K)	10 ⁻⁸ m ²
y_o	9 g/kg
p_{atm}	1 bar
ΔH_0	67400 J/mol
ΔS_0	175 J/(mol · K)
F_b	0.33
RH	0.6

Table 4: Comparison between experimental [9] and numerical results.

Case	Air flow (m ³ /h)	T_{in} (°C)	Inlet mass fraction (g/kg)	Exp. heat (kW/m ³)	Num. heat (kW/m ³)	Exp. T_{bed} (°C)	Num. T_{bed} (°C)
H1	140	25	4	1.76	1.63	29.8	28.3
H2	110	21	12	4.57	4.85	41.0	38.1
H3	93	22	9	3.00	2.96	36.2	35.3
H4	90	22	9	2.56	2.40	36.3	35.3
H5	100	21	12	2.56	2.37	38.5	38.03
H6	80	21	9	2.00	2.16	34.5	34.34

3.3 Effect of Working Conditions

Operating conditions have an essential role in reactor performance in hydration and dehydration processes. As a result, in this section, the effects of solid velocity, air flow rate, and inlet air humidity on the useful heat delivered to the air, air outlet temperature, and bed temperature are investigated.

Figure 2: A comparison between numerical simulation results and experimental study [9]: (a) Temperature, (b) Water vapor mass fraction.

3.3.1 Effect of Solid Velocity. Figure 3(a) shows the variation in reactor bed temperature, T_{bed} , over 8 hours for four solid velocities. The bed temperature increases sharply due to the highly exothermic hydration reaction. When water vapor reaches the reactive front, the reaction rate increases significantly, leading to a rapid rise in temperature.

Initially, the reaction front propagates quickly as vapor diffuses efficiently, and the reaction rate is highest when the material is cold and fully reactive. As the most reactive fraction becomes hydrated, the reaction rate decreases, and the bed temperature approaches a quasi-steady state, where heat release is balanced by conduction, convection, and the declining reaction rate.

Between approximately 4 and 8 hours, a gradual decrease in temperature is observed due to the reduced extent of reaction. As particles approach full hydration, less heat is released, and the bed progressively behaves like a cooling solid with only residual reaction activity. This “tailing-off” behaviour is typical of thermochemical energy storage (TCES) hydration processes, where the driving force—defined as the difference between the

(a)

(b)

Figure 3: Variation of (a) T_{bed} and (b) T_{out} at different solid velocities.

vapor pressure and the equilibrium pressure—decreases over time.

At lower solid velocities, particles remain longer in the reactor, allowing more complete reaction and resulting in a higher and more stable bed temperature, as illustrated in Figure 3(b).

Figure 4 illustrates the temperature distribution within the reactor at different reaction times for a solid velocity of $u_s = 1.5$ cm/h and an air flow rate of 110 m³/h. At $t = 0$ h, the bed is in its initial state prior to hydration, with a uniform temperature of approximately 30 °C.

At $t = 1$ h, localized heating is observed near the inlet region, where the reaction front starts to develop. In this zone, the temperature increases significantly, reaching values of approximately 38 – 40 °C.

Beyond $t = 1$ h, the temperature distribution gradually becomes more uniform throughout the bed as the reaction progresses and heat is distributed by conduction and convection. Over time, the temperature stabilizes, and by $t = 8$ h, the reactor approaches a steady thermal state. Figure 5(a) and (b) show the impact of air flow on T_{out} , T_{bed} , and \dot{q}_{heat} over time for three air volume flow rates ($Q = 80, 110,$ and 140 m³/h) at $u_s = 0.5$ cm/h.

Figure 4: The bed temperature distribution at different reaction times on $u_s=1.5$ cm/h and $Q=110$ m³/h.

(a)

(b)

Figure 5: Variation of (a) T_{bed} and (b) T_{out} and \dot{q}_{heat} .

Humid air passes through the bed, and the humidity increases with Q ; as a result, the hydration reaction rate increases. A higher airflow rate results in more vapor available to react, increasing heat output. At a flow rate of 110 m³/h, high heat output with a manageable pressure drop can be obtained.

Figure 6: Variation of (a) T_{bed} , (b) T_{out} , and \dot{q}_{heat} at different w_{in} .

3.3.2 Effect of Inlet Air Humidity. Figures 6(a) and (b) depict the influence of inlet humidity on T_{bed} , T_{out} , and \dot{q}_{heat} . Inlet air humidity has the greatest effect on the reactor's thermal performance. Heat is released in the reaction of salt and water vapor. The reaction kinetics increase with rising vapor pressure at higher humidity, facilitating hydration. Consequently, increased heat is produced in the bed, leading to the air traversing the bed absorbing this heat and elevating the outflow temperature. At a flow rate of $Q = 110 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$ and a superficial velocity of $u_s = 0.5 \text{ cm/h}$, an increase in w_{in} from 6 g/kg to 12 g/kg elevates T_{bed} from 33 to 44 °C. Increased inlet humidity results in a substantial increase in both the useful heat delivered to the air and the outlet temperature. At $w_{in} = 12 \text{ g/kg}$, the useful heat delivered to the air increases to 3 kW/m^3 , and T_{out} reaches 44 °C. Compared to $w_{in} = 6 \text{ g/kg}$, the useful heat delivered to the air and T_{out} are 0.2 kW/m^3 and 33 °C. Water vapor availability significantly affects the hydration reaction. Although the maximum thermal output was observed at $w_{in} = 12 \text{ g/kg}$, within the practical winter humidity range of 4–9 g/kg, $w_{in} = 9 \text{ g/kg}$ provides the optimal practical condition. Figure 7 shows the hydration conversion, X , at different inlet air humidities at a solid velocity of 0.5 cm/h and an inlet volume

Figure 7: The hydration conversion at different inlet air humidities.

flow rate of $110 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$. The hydration of $\text{SrCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}/6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ increases with the increase in inlet air humidity, because a larger water vapor mass fraction increases the driving force between equilibrium pressure and inlet vapor pressure. The maximum and fastest reaction rate is observed at $w_{in} = 12 \text{ g/kg}$. With greater vapor access, the reaction front saturates quickly, and the salt hydrate reaches full hydration rapidly. To prevent salt swelling and agglomeration, the humidity of 9 g/kg offers a strong reaction rate without moisture-induced instability.

4 Conclusion

A 3D numerical simulation of an open-mode moving-bed thermochemical reactor using $\text{SrCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{SrCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was carried out in COMSOL Multiphysics. This model successfully captured reactor behavior under real conditions by coupling reaction kinetics, fluid flow, and heat and mass transfer.

The highest thermal performance was achieved at a humidity of 12 g/kg and a flow rate of $140 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$; however, these conditions are not practical for continuous operation due to high pressure drop and agglomeration. The inlet humidity of 9 g/kg, flow rate of $110 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$, and solid velocity of 0.5 cm/h were identified as the optimal operating conditions, providing a balance between high performance, manageable pressure drop, and stable hydration behavior.

The developed numerical model provides a valuable tool for the design of moving-bed thermochemical energy storage systems and can support future scale-up as well as integration into building and district heating applications.

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